

WHEN PLATELETS RISE: A PRACTICAL APPROACH TO THROMBOCYTOSIS IN DAILY CLINICAL PRACTICE

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ABSTRACT

Thrombocytosis is a hematologic condition characterized by an elevated platelet count in the peripheral blood above the upper age-adjusted reference limit, typically $>450 \times 10^9/L$. It is broadly classified as primary (clonal), most commonly associated with myeloproliferative neoplasms such as essential thrombocythemia, and secondary (reactive), occurring in response to infections, inflammatory disorders, iron deficiency anemia, tissue injury, malignancy, or following splenectomy. In daily practice, reactive thrombocytosis predominates and is generally transient with a benign clinical course. The clinical significance of thrombocytosis depends not only on the degree of platelet elevation but also on the underlying condition, platelet function, and coexisting risk factors. While secondary forms are rarely associated with major complications, primary thrombocytosis carries an increased risk of thrombotic and hemorrhagic events, as well as the potential for progression to myelofibrosis or acute leukemia. Timely differentiation between reactive and clonal forms is essential for appropriate therapeutic decision-making and long-term prognostic assessment.

Keywords: thrombocytosis, inflammation, iron deficiency, myeloproliferative neoplasms, clonal diseases.

Introduction

Thrombocytosis is an abnormality defined as an increase in the platelet count in peripheral blood above $450 \times 10^9/L$. It is observed in a wide range of conditions, including both benign disorders and clonal hematologic diseases. In clinical practice, it is often detected incidentally in asymptomatic patients and raises the question of the seriousness of its underlying cause. In many cases, the diagnostic process requires time to accurately distinguish between a reactive process and a clonal etiology. In addition to identifying the cause, assessing the potential risk of complications (most commonly thrombotic events) is of significant importance. The contemporary diagnostic approach to thrombocytosis is based on a combination of clinical findings, basic laboratory parameters, and specialized molecular genetic investigations, which enable timely diagnosis and appropriate clinical management.

This review provides a practice-oriented overview of the most common types of thrombocytosis, aiming to facilitate the work of specialists from various fields by presenting the most important clues leading to its underlying causes, the relevant diagnostic methods, and a simplified management algorithm for everyday clinical practice.

Classification of Thrombocytosis

Depending on the underlying causes, thrombocytosis can be classified into the following groups:

I. Reactive (Secondary) Thrombocytosis

This is the most common form and represents a physiological response of the bone marrow to external stimuli. It occurs more frequently and accounts for approximately 80–90% of all cases of thrombocytosis in clinical practice [1]. The main causes of reactive thrombocytosis include acute and chronic infections, inflammatory and autoimmune diseases, iron deficiency anemia, solid tumors and hematologic malignancies, postsurgical states and splenectomy, blood loss, and hemolysis. The most significant characteristics of these conditions are their transient nature, absence of clonal mutations, and low thrombotic risk, with management

primarily directed toward treatment of the underlying disease.

II. Clonal Thrombocytosis

This form is associated with myeloproliferative neoplasms, in which thrombocytosis results from autonomous megakaryocytic proliferation without external stimulation. The main nosological entities in this group include essential thrombocythemia (ET), polycythemia vera (PV), and primary myelofibrosis (PMF), including the prefibrotic phase. These conditions are characterized by persistent thrombocytosis driven by mutations in genes such as JAK2, CALR, and MPL, an increased risk of arterial and venous thrombosis, and a paradoxical risk of hemorrhagic complications in cases of extreme thrombocytosis.

III. Hereditary (Familial) Thrombocytosis

This group includes very rare genetically determined conditions characterized by mutations in the THPO or MPL genes, absence of malignant potential, and diagnosis typically established in childhood or early adulthood. The clinical significance of thrombocytosis is primarily determined by the assessment of the risk of thrombotic and hemorrhagic complications, as well as the risk of clonal evolution in cases of underlying hematologic malignancy. Misinterpretation of thrombocytosis carries a dual risk: unnecessary treatment on one hand, and failure to diagnose a serious underlying condition on the other. Underestimation may delay the diagnosis of a myeloproliferative neoplasm, whereas overdiagnosis in reactive forms may lead to unjustified antithrombotic or cytotoxic therapy.

To reduce the risk of diagnostic errors, the evaluation of thrombocytosis requires a structured diagnostic approach that enables rapid differentiation between reactive and clonal forms, accurate risk assessment, and appropriate clinical management. This makes thrombocytosis a significant diagnostic and therapeutic challenge, with a direct impact on patient prognosis and quality of life.

Epidemiological Data

Epidemiology of Reactive Thrombocytosis

In hospital practice, the frequency of reactive thrombocytosis is particularly high and is observed in approximately 1.5–7% of all hospitalized patients, with the majority of cases associated with acute infectious or inflammatory conditions [2], predominantly bacterial infections, especially in adult patients [1]. A significant proportion of benign thrombocytosis is due to iron deficiency anemia, which accounts for 15–30% of cases. This type of thrombocytosis is more commonly observed in women of reproductive age and in patients with chronic blood loss, and is considered to result from increased thrombopoietin production and dysregulation of the megakaryocytic lineage [3]. Postoperative conditions, particularly following splenectomy, represent another cause of reactive thrombocytosis. Transient thrombocytosis develops in more than 70% of patients after splenectomy, and in most cases follows a self-limiting course within several months after surgical removal of the spleen. In the pediatric population, benign thrombocytosis predominates, with more than 95% of cases in childhood being secondary in nature, most commonly associated with infections, and generally without long-term clinical consequences [4].

Epidemiology of Clonal Thrombocytosis

Clonal causes of persistent thrombocytosis are most commonly associated with the classical BCR-ABL1-negative myeloproliferative neoplasms, including ET, PV, and PMF. Epidemiological data indicate that the incidence of PV ranges between 0.5 and 4.0 cases per 100,000 person-years, while ET has a slightly higher incidence of approximately 1.1 to 2.0 cases per 100,000 person-years [5]. This wide range reflects diagnostic limitations across different geographical regions. In the United States, the incidence of ET has been reported at approximately 1.5 new cases per 100,000 individuals, which is comparable to data from other Western populations [6]. The median age at diagnosis is around 60 years, and the condition is rare in younger individuals. Women are more frequently affected, with a female-to-male ratio of approximately 2:1 in some larger series [7]. PMF occurs less frequently, with an incidence of approximately 0.3 to 2.0 cases per 100,000 person-years. Its clinical course often includes progressive bone marrow fibrosis, cytopenias, and an increased risk of transformation to acute leukemia, resulting in significantly shorter overall survival compared with ET and PV [8].

Management of benign (reactive) thrombocytosis

In reactive thrombocytosis, the main therapeutic principle is directed toward treatment of the underlying condition rather than directly targeting the platelet count. In most cases, the elevation in platelet count represents a physiological compensatory response and

does not require specific hematological therapy. In the presence of acute or chronic inflammation, infection, or tissue injury, the platelet count usually normalizes in parallel with resolution of the underlying process. In these situations, the routine use of antiplatelet agents is not indicated, as it has not been shown to reduce the risk of thrombosis and may increase the risk of bleeding. Particular attention is required in cases of thrombocytosis associated with iron deficiency anemia. In this context, correction of iron deficiency leads to gradual normalization of the platelet count. Persistence of thrombocytosis after adequate treatment of iron deficiency necessitates re-evaluation and exclusion of a concomitant clonal disorder. In patients with malignancies or following splenectomy, thrombocytosis is often part of a broader prothrombotic profile. In such cases, the decision to initiate antithrombotic prophylaxis should be based on an overall assessment of vascular risk rather than on the platelet count as an isolated parameter.

In summary, in benign forms, the key management approach includes observation, treatment of the underlying condition, and avoidance of unnecessary pharmacological intervention unless additional risk factors are present.

Clinical Significance and Management of Clonal Thrombocytosis

The clinical significance of clonal thrombocytosis is determined by two main factors: an increased thrombotic risk and the potential for clonal evolution of the disease, which varies depending on the associated hematologic malignancy. ET is associated with a significantly increased risk of arterial and venous thrombosis. Additionally, platelets in ET exhibit functional abnormalities that not only increase thrombotic risk but are paradoxically also associated with hemorrhagic manifestations. When platelet counts exceed $1000 \times 10^9/L$, they may acquire the capacity to absorb and eliminate the activity of von Willebrand factor (vWf), leading to an acquired coagulopathy.

In PV thrombotic risk is further increased by changes in hematocrit levels and the presence of the JAK2 mutation. PMF, which has the most unfavorable clinical course among Philadelphia-negative myeloproliferative neoplasms, is characterized by a pronounced tendency for rapid progression to acute leukemia and reduced survival. It represents a diagnostic challenge, particularly in its early prefibrotic phase, when the only manifestation may be mild, seemingly benign thrombocytosis.

Table 1 summarizes the most common causes of thrombocytosis in clinical practice and their main characteristics.

Table 1

Thrombocytosis by nosological groups – etiology, mechanisms, and clinical features

Nosological Group	Type of Thrombocytosis	Main Mechanism	Typical Clinical Features	Thrombotic Risk
Inflammatory and infectious diseases	Reactive	Cytokine-mediated stimulation (IL-6 → ↑ thrombopoietin)	Correlation with inflammatory activity; normalization with treatment	Low
Iron deficiency anemia	Reactive	Increased megakaryocyte sensitivity to thrombopoietin; compensatory hematopoiesis	Often moderate to marked thrombocytosis; possible coexistence with other causes	Usually low
Malignancies (solid tumors)	Reactive / Paraneoplastic	Cytokines, growth factors, tumor-induced thrombopoiesis	Associated with poorer prognosis	Moderate
Post-splenectomy state	Reactive	Reduced sequestration and increased platelet survival	Often pronounced in the early postoperative period	Moderate
Myeloproliferative neoplasms (ET, PV, PMF, CML)	Clonal	Autonomous megakaryocytic proliferation (JAK2, CALR, MPL)	Persistent thrombocytosis, splenomegaly, microvascular symptoms	High
Hereditary thrombocytosis	Clonal / Genetic	Mutations in genes related to the thrombopoietin pathway	Rare; often positive family history	Variable

A major challenge in clinical practice is how to rapidly differentiate reactive thrombocytosis, which carries a low thrombotic risk, from clonal thrombocytosis, which is associated not only with an increased

thrombotic risk but also with the potential for clonal evolution. Figure 1 represents a simplified approach to the diagnosis of thrombocytosis.

Figure 1. Simplified Diagnostic algorithm in thrombocytosis Abbreviations: CBC- complete blood count; PLT- platelets; Jak(Janus Kinase); CALR(Calreticulin), MPL(Myeloproliferative leucemia oncogene); NGS (Next generation sequencing); MKC-megakaryocyte; vW- von Willebrand factor

The main distinguishing features between reactive and clonal thrombocytosis are outlined in Table 2.

Table 2

Reactive versus Clonal Thrombocytosis – Key Differences

Characteristic	Reactive (Secondary) Thrombocytosis	Clonal (Primary) Thrombocytosis
Underlying cause	Response to a systemic stimulus (inflammation, infection, iron deficiency, tumor)	Autonomous megakaryocytic proliferation
Nature of the process	Polyclonal, compensatory	Monoclonal, neoplastic
Duration	Usually transient	Persistent
Platelet count level	Moderately elevated	Markedly and persistently elevated
Inflammatory markers (CRP, ESR)	Often elevated	Normal
Iron status	Often deficient	Normal
Molecular markers (JAK2, CALR, MPL)	Negative	Frequently positive
Bone marrow findings	Reactive megakaryocytosis	Atypical megakaryocytic proliferation with clustering in MF
Splenomegaly	Rare	Common
Thrombotic risk	Low	Moderate to high
Hemorrhagic risk	Minimal	Increased (at very high platelet counts)
Management	Treatment of the underlying condition	Risk stratification and specific therapy

Clinical risks in thrombocytosis – When does an elevated platelet count matter?

The risk of thrombotic complications is highly dependent on the underlying etiology of thrombocytosis. In reactive forms, it is generally low and primarily determined by the underlying condition rather than by the platelet count itself. Inflammation, infections, or iron deficiency anemia rarely lead to thrombosis directly related to thrombocytosis. Exceptions include conditions such as active malignancy, severe systemic inflammation, or post-splenectomy status, in which thrombocytosis may contribute to the overall prothrombotic risk (for example, patients with intermediate forms of thalassemia following splenectomy are at increased risk of thrombotic events).

From the perspective of absolute platelet count, mild to moderate thrombocytosis is usually not associated with an immediate clinical risk, particularly when transient and attributable to a clearly reactive cause. Its clinical significance increases in cases of persistent and marked elevation exceeding $1000 \times 10^9/L$. In extreme thrombocytosis, the risk becomes more complex—along with thrombosis, the likelihood of bleeding also increases. Platelets exert functional effects that sustain systemic inflammation, creating a vicious cycle in which platelets perpetuate the inflammatory process, which in turn leads to increased platelet production. Microvascular symptoms such as erythromelalgia and transient neurological complaints may be considered early warning signs, where platelet activation and inflammation result in functional disturbances of the microcirculation without structural thrombosis.

In this context, decisions regarding antiplatelet and cytoreductive therapy cannot be based solely on

platelet count but should take into account inflammatory activity, signs of hemostatic disturbance, and individual vascular risk. It is particularly important to recognize situations in which aggressive antithrombotic therapy may increase hemorrhagic risk, as well as the opposite scenario—underestimation of thrombotic risk in patients with relatively moderate thrombocytosis but increased platelet activity.

In contrast, in clonal thrombocytosis, platelets are often functionally altered and actively participate in the thrombotic process. Another important aspect is their functional heterogeneity. In clonal thrombocytosis, platelets are not only increased in number but also exhibit a greater tendency toward activation, adhesion, and interaction with the endothelium. This explains why thrombotic risk does not correlate linearly with the absolute platelet count and why some patients develop vascular events at relatively moderate levels. Arterial and venous thromboses, including stroke, myocardial infarction, and thromboses in atypical vascular territories, represent a major source of morbidity. The risk is further increased in older patients, those with a history of previous thrombotic events, and in the presence of specific molecular characteristics (e.g., JAK2 positivity).

Clinical attention should also be given to the hemorrhagic risk associated with very high platelet counts exceeding $1200 \times 10^9/L$. In such cases, an acquired deficiency of vWf often develops, clinically manifesting as mucocutaneous bleeding, epistaxis, or gastrointestinal hemorrhage.

Clinical Indicators of Clonal Thrombocytosis

In clinical practice, several “red flags” warrant increased suspicion of clonal thrombocytosis. Alarm features include:

1. persistent thrombocytosis for more than 6 months without a clear reactive cause;
2. splenomegaly;
3. microvascular ischemia of the extremities;
4. increasing platelet count or values exceeding $1000 \times 10^9/L$.

Therapeutic Approach to Clonal Thrombocytosis

Management is a process in which the appropriate approach is guided by addressing several key questions:

1. **What should be the treatment goal?**

In clonal thrombocytosis, the objective is not merely to reduce platelet count, but to:

- decrease thrombotic risk (arterial/venous thrombosis);

- limit hemorrhagic risk (especially in extreme thrombocytosis and acquired von Willebrand disease);
- control microvascular symptoms (headache, erythromelalgia, visual disturbances).

2. **Who requires active therapy?**

This decision is based on risk factors for thrombotic events. According to current reviews and recommendations for ET, risk is stratified into four categories—very low, low, intermediate, and high—based on age, history of thrombosis, JAK2 mutation status, and other factors [6,9]. Table 3 summarizes management strategies regarding both antiplatelet and cytoreductive therapy in clonal thrombocytosis.

Table 3

Practical approach to risk stratification and management of essential thrombocythemia (ET)

Risk Group	Criteria	Recommended Therapeutic Strategy
High risk	Age ≥ 60 years and/or history of arterial or venous thrombosis	Cytoreductive therapy (first-line: hydroxyurea; alternative: interferon- α); Antithrombotic therapy (low-dose aspirin, if no contraindications); Strict control of cardiovascular risk factors
Low risk	Age < 60 years and no history of thrombosis	Low-dose aspirin, if no contraindications (especially in JAK2 V617F-positive patients); Control of cardiovascular risk factors; Cytoreduction is not routinely indicated but may be considered in cases of extreme thrombocytosis, symptomatic microvascular ischemia, or acquired von Willebrand syndrome

The table systematizes therapeutic management according to the risk of vascular complications.

3. **When should aspirin be used with caution or avoided?** One of the most common clinical questions concerns the use of aspirin—when it should be administered and when it should be avoided. Low-dose aspirin is standard therapy for many patients with ET/PV, particularly in the presence of microvascular symptoms and/or increased arterial risk, except in cases with an elevated bleeding risk [10,11]. Discontinuation of aspirin should be considered in cases of extreme thrombocytosis (approximately $>1000-1500 \times 10^9/L$) due to the risk of acquired von Willebrand syndrome (avWS) [10,12]. A practical rule in patients with very high

platelet counts is to first exclude avWS. A second practical approach is to initiate cytoreductive therapy before implementing an antiplatelet strategy.

4. **Cytoreductive therapy** represents the cornerstone of management in patients at high thrombotic risk. Table 4 summarizes the indications for initiating cytoreductive treatment [6].

If thrombocytosis is part of PV/PMF, platelet count should be managed within the framework of overall PV therapy [13]. In PV, achieving hematocrit control in combination with an antiplatelet strategy is essential. In PMF, management may include JAK inhibitors when indicated, with thrombocytosis treated according to the individual risk profile and clinical presentation.

Indications and therapeutic options for cytoreduction in clonal Thrombocytosis

Category	Indication / Therapeutic Option	Clinical Notes
Indications for initiation of cytoreduction	High thrombotic risk	Advanced age and/or history of prior thrombosis
	Intolerance or contraindications to aspirin	Increased thrombotic risk in the absence of antiplatelet prophylaxis
	Extreme thrombocytosis	Risk of bleeding (acquired von Willebrand syndrome) and thrombosis
	Perioperative conditions	Additional transient thrombotic risk
	Pregnancy	Individual risk–benefit assessment
First-line therapy	Hydroxyurea	Most commonly used in high-risk patients, especially those >60 years of age
	Pegylated interferon- α	Preferred in younger patients and in planned or established pregnancy; suitable for long-term control without HU
Alternative / Second-line	Anagrelide	In cases of intolerance or contraindications to HU/IFN; requires caution due to cardiovascular adverse effects

Emergency Situations

In cases of symptomatic extreme thrombocytosis accompanied by acute thrombotic complications or severe bleeding associated with avWS, rapid platelet reduction by thrombocytapheresis may be required as a bridge to subsequent cytoreductive therapy. AvWS is one of the frequently underestimated complications in clonal thrombocytosis. The pathophysiological basis of avWS in clonal thrombocytosis is related to the markedly elevated platelet count and the accelerated adsorption and clearance of high-molecular-weight vWF multimers from the platelet surface. As a result, a functional deficiency of vWF develops, resembling type 2 von Willebrand disease, with impaired primary hemostasis.

Clinically, avWS presents with mucocutaneous bleeding manifestations such as epistaxis, gingival bleeding, easy bruising, and gastrointestinal hemorrhage [12]. The risk of bleeding is highest in patients with extreme thrombocytosis, usually at platelet counts exceeding $1000\text{--}1500 \times 10^9/\text{L}$, and is significantly more common in clonal than in reactive forms. The presence of avWS has important implications for therapeutic decision-making. In such cases, routine use of antiplatelet therapy, particularly aspirin, may lead to clinically significant bleeding and should be avoided until platelet count is reduced. Therefore, in patients with very high platelet counts in the context of clonal thrombocytosis, targeted assessment of vWF activity and multimer analysis is recommended prior to initiating antiplatelet therapy. Treatment of avWS in myeloproliferative neoplasms is primarily directed at the underlying disease.

In conclusion, thrombocytosis is a heterogeneous condition. Differentiation between reactive and clonal forms, assessment of associated clinical phenomena, and integration of thrombotic, hemorrhagic, and inflammatory risk are essential for optimal clinical management. Understanding this complex interplay is key to an individualized patient-centered approach and to optimizing therapeutic strategies in both benign and clonal forms of thrombocytosis.

References

1. Schafer B *New England Journal of Medicine*, (<https://www.nejm.org/doi/full/10.1056/NEJMr035363>).
2. Buss DH, Cashell AW, O'Connor ML, Richards F 2nd, Case LD. Occurrence, etiology, and clinical significance of extreme thrombocytosis: a study of 280 cases. *Am J Med*. 1994 Mar;96(3):247-53. doi: 10.1016/0002-9343(94)90150-3. PMID: 8154513.
3. Skoda RC. Thrombocytosis. *Hematology Am Soc Hematol Educ Program*. 2009;2009(1):159–167. doi:10.1182/asheducation-2009.1.159
4. Harrison CN, Bareford D, Butt N, Campbell P, Conneally E, Drummond M, Erber W, Everington T, Green AR, Hall GW, Hunt BJ, Ludlam CA, Murrin R, Nelson-Piercy C, Radia DH, Reilly JT, Van der Walt J, Wilkins B, McMullin MF; British Committee for Standards in Haematology. Guideline for investigation and management of adults and children presenting with a thrombocytosis. *Br J Haematol*. 2010 May;149(3):352-75. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2141.2010.08122.x. Epub 2010 Mar 15. PMID: 20331456.
5. Population-based incidence study(LWW Hemasphere)–ET incidence 0.2–2.5/100 000 per year. https://journals.lww.com/hemasphere/fulltext/2023/08003/pb2236_population_based_incidence_of_essential.2094.aspx
6. Tefferi A, Gangat N, Loscocco GG, Guglielmelli P, Szuber N, Pardanani A, Orazi A, Barbui T, Vannucchi AM. Essential Thrombocythemia: A Review. *JAMA*. 2025 Feb 25;333(8):701-714. doi: 10.1001/jama.2024.25349. PMID: 39869325.
7. Accurso V, Santoro M, Mancuso S, Napolitano M, Carlisi M, Mattana M, Russo C, Di Stefano A, Sirocchi D, Siragusa S. The Essential Thrombocythemia in 2020: What We Know and Where We Still Have to Dig Deep. *Clin Med Insights Blood Disord*. 2020 Dec 28;13:2634853520978210. doi: 10.1177/2634853520978210. PMID: 33447121; PMCID: PMC7780200.

8. Shallis RM, Zeidan AM, Wang R, Podoltsev NA. Epidemiology of the Philadelphia Chromosome-Negative Classical Myeloproliferative Neoplasms. *Hematol Oncol Clin North Am*. 2021 Apr;35(2):177-189. doi: 0.1016/j.hoc.2020.11.005. Epub 2021 Jan 4. PMID: 33641862.
9. Tiede A, Rand JH, Budde U, Ganser A, Federici AB. How I treat the acquired von Willebrand syndrome. *Blood*. 2011 Jun 23;117(25):6777-85. doi: 10.1182/blood-2010-11-297580. Epub 2011 May 3. PMID: 21540459.
10. Cattaneo M. Aspirin in essential thrombocythemia. For whom? What formulation? What regimen? *Haematologica*. 2023 Jun 1;108(6):1487-1499. doi: 10.3324/haematol.2022.281388. PMID: 36632735; PMCID: PMC10230439.
11. Alberta Health Services. Essential Thrombocythemia. Cancer Care Alberta Clinical Practice Guideline LYHE-012. Edmonton (AB): Alberta Health Services; [cited 2026 Feb 23]. Available from: <https://www.albertahealthservices.ca/assets/info/hp/cancer/if-hp-cancer-guide-lyhe012-et.pdf>
12. Awada H, Voso MT, Guglielmelli P, Gurnari C. Essential Thrombocythemia and Acquired von Willebrand Syndrome: The Shadowlands between Thrombosis and Bleeding. *Cancers (Basel)*. 2020 Jun 30;12(7):1746. doi: 10.3390/cancers12071746. PMID: 32629973; PMCID: PMC7407619.
13. Loguidice CT. Essential thrombocythemia and polycythemia vera treatments are moving toward disease modification. *Oncology Live*. 2022 Aug 4;23(15):24.